

Kanavera and Sulasa Jataka As A Source to Understand the Social History of Early India

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Abstract:

My research topic was related on the Kanavera and Sulasa jataka and I have analysed the social history as a broad category that includes the different sections like political, administrative, economic and social aspects which gives us better understanding to study about the Ancient India. Buddha is portrayed as the protagonist of each of these stories, they narrated the incidents of his past life, when he was bodhisatta. Kanavera and Sulasa jataka as a source which gives us information about the social stratification of the society and highlights the issues of gender and sexuality. The gender roles and identities were very well portrayed in the Buddhist literature and also defined the social life of women. We came to know about the different social structure depicted in these narratives which reflected the various norms and conditions prevailing in the society. The political system that existed was based on the absolute monarchy which had to be transformed in which it would be an important instrument of social and political change as mentioned in Buddhist literature. We came to know about the Ancient India which spread their culture ethics by narrating the jataka tales told by Buddhist to inspire the local population. I would like to conclude by saying that jataka throws significant light on the political and economic condition of people as part of society and not directly related to the Buddhist beliefs but considers its moral, ethics and principles. These texts were structured in such a manner that gives the evidence of literary as well as the Buddhist tradition.

Key Words:

Kanavera, Sulasa, jataka, Buddhist, Ancient India.

The *Jataka* tales were composed around the fifth century which highlighted the previous birth stories of Buddha in the Pali literature. There were around 550 stories found in Buddhist literature. We can find the verses of the religious teaching of Buddha in the *Khuddakanikaya* text and later on in which stories were added by the commentators in the *Jatakas*. All the narrative starts with the *Paccupannavatthu* or introduction which describes the story about the present life and which further brings the previous life story known as *Atitavatthu*. Each narrative presents the Buddha similar to the characters present in previous life and this final section known as *Samodhana*. This paper on the whole tries to focus on the narratives present in the *kanavera* and *sulasa Jatakas* and how these sources are fundamentally important to trace the social history in a broader sense as includes the political-administrative, economic and cultural aspect of the society.

In world literature, *jatakas* were considered as the popular literary collection. The question that arises is that why is it an important source to study Ancient India? The descriptive text understood the concepts and approach of the narrative which are also embroiled in Buddhist norms.¹ It was a fundamental narrative of early India which highlighted some of the lessons

¹ Kumkum Roy, 'Justice in the Jatakas', *Social Scientist*, 1996, 24:4/6, pp.26-27.

from the daily lives of the local people because it adopted the narrative approach. Both the sources are also important to understand the concepts of social stratification which includes the class-caste identities, idea of gender and sexuality and also traces the social position from higher social order to the lowest group of the society.

In *kanavera jataka*, bodhisattva as a thief was captured by the guards. A prostitute saw him and fell in love with him. In desire, she tries to bribe the captors and have the innocent man executed in his place so that he could become her husband. The man feared that she would someday fall in love with another man and would kill him in return. So he tries to flee away from there. The *sulasa jataka* presented the similar narrative but here bodhisatta was a tree fairy and in the end the thief tries to steal her wealth and wanted to kill her but she kills him first here and the bodhisatta noted women's presence of mind who act intelligently according to the situation. From these narratives we will directly analyse the broad category of social history that includes the economic and political aspect of the society.

We get the reference about the leadership in these *jatakas* as they give us information about the kings and how they govern their kingdom. These *jatakas* also revolve around the king's character as they depicted them as the righteous king as there was a king mentioned in *kanavera* and *sulasa jataka* who wanted to conduct the fair practices in his kingdom. Prof.Kumkum Roy presented the similar view that the king was expected to be impartial and do justice to the people.² For instance, in *kanavera* and *sulasa jataka*, the king was portrayed as the champion of law and justice, this brief us about the law and order prevalent in Ancient Indian society. These literary texts also mention the various settlements like *gama*, *nagra* and *mahanagara* which means the narratives depict the numerous cities and settlements in the countryside which accommodate the large population in the town. These were the understandings we get to know about the kingship and settlement pattern and how political-administration was a part of the society.

In the economic context, these *jataka* gives us a better understanding of the economic situation of that period and highlights the various types of financial activities that boost up the economy of the society. There are references of *setthi* who was a businessman with a strong economic

² *Ibid*, p.30.

base and were considered to be important members in the urban community.³ The *gahapati* were also an important socio-economic group who were considered important for the society and were taxpayers. Uma Chakravarti tries to differentiate between the Buddhist scheme and the Brahmanical scheme and according to her the power of Buddhist scheme comes from inclusion of the *gahapati* in the social stratification and on the other hand the Brahmanical scheme was a complete failure as didn't include them in the stratification that is why presenting the partial and distorted view of the society.⁴ The appearance of the *ganika* into the economic sphere and in an agrarian system which is based on the private control of land and labour activity.⁵ The most important relationship in the society was that of master and worker who should provide the work in return expecting them to be loyal and serve to them.⁶ In my knowledge based on the translations, the lower class has always been the sufferers which suggests the division of society is not only based on political or social norms but also on economic bases.

In social context, the *jatakas* generally present the five virtues or *pancasila* that should be avoided by everyone which is killing, stealing, no intoxicants, no desirableness and false speeches but we came to know the opposite stand in both the *jatakas*. Another important moral conduct was the truth and wisdom which shows the distinctive quality of a person which we didn't find in any of these narratives. Also, the *sulasa jataka* gives us the example of gift giving ritual practiced by the master as this benefits themselves (*karma*) and others who were dependent on them. Based upon this *jataka*, we think the way up for a good quality of life can be found in the nature of good moral action. In these *jatakas*, there were reflections of the social and gender inequality as the narrative mentioned about the unpleasant condition of the women and slaves in the society. It was believed that she had to be controlled by the dominant class and there should be restrictions on the privileges of adulthood.⁷ Contrary to it, both the narratives showed that women were dominantly involved in adultery practice. Sometimes, the

³ Upinder Singh, *A History of Ancient and Early Medieval India: From Stone Age to the 12 Century*, Dorling Kindersley: India, 2016, pp.288.

⁴ Uma Chakravarti, *Everyday Lives, Everyday Histories: Beyond Kings and Brahmanas of 'Ancient' India*, Tulika Books: New Delhi, 2006, pp.65-66.

⁵ Uma Chakravarti, *The Social Dimensions of Early Buddhism*, Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers : New Delhi, 1996, pp.177.

⁶ *Ibid*, p.180.

⁷ Uma Chakravarti, *Everyday Lives, Everyday Histories: Beyond Kings and Brahmanas of 'Ancient' India*, p.180.

image of the women was portrayed as the dominant one with an uncontrollable desire. The completely different view can be seen in Tanya Roy's work who studies the I.B.Honors work on the study of women in Buddhist philosophy and argues that women had much more freedom than ever before they had.⁸ With the growth of Buddhism the women became an important part of the society and their role was not restricted to as the wife, mothers or spinster. For instance, *ganikas* were the masters in their own household as *jatakas* stories reflect the wealthy influential courtesans who own household, maid, bodyguards and enjoy great freedom yet are dependent in male -dominant society. But we noted from the *kanavera* and *sulasa jatakas* about the social inequalities and the notion of *karma* which gives us the idea about the individual ranking in the society. In my opinion, the notion of *karma* presented in this *jataka* and this can be further understood as a cycle of birth or rebirth which is inexplicitly related to the caste system. As far as we know, the Buddhist religion rejected the idea of the caste system which further explicitly recognized the oppressed section of the society and paved the way for prostitutes and other lowest social groups. This shows us how much social and gender hierarchical norms were deeply rooted in the early Indian literature in the male dominating society. The *kanavera* and *sulasa jatakas* represent that women enjoyed their power and status in the restricted society and also we get the various instances where the *dasis* or slaves from the lower category restricted to the household spaces. This is the general social pattern and the behaviour towards the women which occurs from the defective consideration of their role in the sphere of social economic aspect.

After analysing these two narratives the question arises is that does patriarchy reflect in the Buddhist order? what we found in the Buddhist literature is that they always distrust women and put the blame of all misfortune on the women.⁹ This picture was revealed in the *kanavera jataka* story of the present where Buddha warns the bodhisattva from falling in love with the women. In both the narratives there is a depiction that women were irresponsible outside their household space as they remained in their houses and usually the male members went outside on their behalf. The idea of karma is also attached here as due to the ungrateful deeds done in previous birth, women were compelled to take up the profession of prostitute. The literature

⁸ Taniya Roy, 'The Notion of Objectifying Women: As Represented in the Jatakas', *Proceedings of Indian History Congress*, vol.73, 2012, pp. 127.

⁹ Uma Chakravarti, *Everyday Lives, Everyday Histories: Beyond Kings and Brahmanas of 'Ancient' India*, p.211.

portrayed the women in a negative light and with their role limited to sexual activities. The *kanavera* and *sulasa jataka* depicted the story of a prostitute who falls in love with another man by betraying the honest man and put all the blame on the women's if either man flees or died away due to his own karma but these stories always reflect this female untrustworthiness and faithlessness in an obnoxious manner which further adding to the warnings to the bodhisattva as and laity. The Buddhist tradition didn't bother to address the question of gender equality as it faces the social economic disparities especially by the *ganikas* or *dasis*. But one can argue that there was not full-fledged exploitation of the slaves as work was assigned to their capacity, they were supplied with food and wages ,and granted them leave occasionally. The social injustice was justified on the notion of karma as they have committed the sins in their previous birth so it could be rectified by doing the good deeds into the social conduct.

The Buddhist tradition also deals with the idea of social stratification which is identified through the various terms like *jati*, *kula* and *kamma*. For social stratification, Buddhist prefer to use the term *kula* instead of *jaati* and according to them to rebirth in the high *kula* of *khattiya*, *brahman* or *gahapati* one should have good behaviour and meritorious deeds.¹⁰ Uma Chakravarti in the book *the social dimensions of Early Buddhism* put emphasis on the system of social stratification which shows the sharp reality of the society.¹¹ Social hierarchy played an important role in maintaining the sharp differences in the social order. We find the different social structure in the society from high order (king or *setthi*) to the lower social group (*ganika*, *dasis* and *nagarapala*) which describes the daily social norms and conditions of that time. In the Buddhist text, *gahapati* generally related to the agricultural activity and *setthi* category was also mentioned but none of these categories were related to the *Vaishya* class of brahmanical order. Similarly, it didn't mention about the *Shudra* class instead mention about the *dasas* and *karmakars* who serve these upper class varna, especially the *gahapatis*. Despite rejecting the idea of caste system they believe in it. Uma Chakravarti clearly tries to study the various social categories beyond the social stratification and caste system as indicated through the social stratification.¹² The society indicates the slavery practice which throw light on the social inequality among various groups. It is important to understand the extreme conditions of their

¹⁰ *Ibid*, p.64.

¹¹ Uma Chakravarti, *The Social Dimensions of Early Buddhism*, pp.108-113.

¹² Uma Chakravarti, *Everyday Lives, Everyday Histories: Beyond Kings and Brahmanas of 'Ancient' India*, p.59-64.

poverty and impoverishment of these sections contrary to the other section who was prosperous.

I would like to conclude by saying that in this paper we have analysed the *kanavera* and *sulasa jatakas* to understand the importance of social history which is also much relevant to contemporary times. The *jatakas* tales were part of the oral traditions which were orally recited by people but later they were assembled and made some adjustments to the narrative by the local people. The *jatakas* were the independent source which gives us knowledge about the political, economic and social cultural processes of Ancient India dated between fifth century and third century. These were compiled not at a particular place or by person. So, there might be the possibility of the omission found in the narrative. We found many complexities in the *jataka* stories which is also a fundamental source to look at contemporary practices. Hence, the political-administrative, economy and social cultural activities found in the *jataka* narrative were interconnected together.

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